

THEORITICAL VIEWS ON TERMS, TERMINOLOGY AND TERMINOLOGICAL SYSTEM IN LINGUISTICS

Hilola Sotvoldiyeva

FDU ingliz tili amaliy kursi kafedراسi dotsenti

Erkinova Oynura Qudratillo qizi

FDU magistranti

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15285410>

Abstract. Terminology, the study of terms and their use, is a crucial component of linguistic research, especially in the context of specialized fields like science, technology, and law. This article explores the theoretical views on terms, terminology and terminological system emphasizing methodologies of term formation, research, and the sociocultural factors influencing terminological development. It includes the features of term in linguistics connecting to what science, fields are needed and exhaustive description for terminology, the usage of its system.

Key words: terminology, technical term, terminological system, systematicity, semiological expression, designatum

Terminology serves as the linguistic backbone of specialized knowledge domains, facilitating communication among professionals and ensuring clarity and precision in discourse. The study of terminology encompasses various theoretical frameworks that aim to understand how terms are created, developed, and standardized across languages. A term is traditionally defined as a word or expression that has a specific meaning in a particular context. This definition interlinks the linguistic and conceptual dimensions of terminology, which is crucial for both English and Uzbek.

A term (lat. terminus - a check, a limit) is a word or a combination of words that is a clear and stable expression of a specific concept specific to a field of science and technology. A term is a word or combination of words that clearly means a concept used in science, technology, and art. Unlike common literary words, terms are not characterized by expressiveness and ambiguity. O.S. Akhmanova states that "... linguistic terminology is not a simple set of terms like any other terminology, but a unique semiological system"

Modern terminological works note various properties of the term, and linguists agree that the term is related to a scientific concept. On other features of the term, scientists' opinions differ. According to our research, the obligatory and constant features of an industry term are: 1) a close connection with a scientific and technical concept of a specific field of knowledge; 2) systematicity, manifested in synonymous, antonymous, generic and whole-partial relations

with other terms of a given terminology and/or terminology system; 3) the need for a definition.

The connection of a term with the subject of scientific and technical thought is one of the main features of a term, distinguishing it from commonly used words and other types of special lexical units. Each term, both a term-word and a term-phrase, exists in an inseparable connection with a scientific concept. The connection between the result of scientific and technical development (artifact, process) and its name (term) is realized only through the concept. The term performs the function of naming a scientific concept.

Due to their systematic nature, the terms of a specific field of science, technology or sphere of activity are closely interconnected with each other and united into a structured organization. Until recently, a structured organization of terms of a certain field of knowledge was called "terminology". Thus, well-known terminologists K. Ya. Averbukh, S. G. Kazarina, R. Yu. Kobrin, V. F. Novodranova, V. N. Prokhorova used the term "terminology" in their dissertation research. In recent decades, Russian linguists have also used the word "terminological system", and much more actively than "terminology". The topics of dissertation research, for example, N. V. Vinogradova, M. N. Ozolina, I. A. Pushkareva, A. K. Suleimanova, I. B. Tikhonova testify to this. K. Suleimanova in her dissertation "The terminology system of the oil industry and its functioning in the professional discourse of a specialist" believes that the terminology system is related to the system of concepts of a certain area of knowledge and is a set of terms determined by the culture of the country and the mentality of the people. A. V. M. Leichik approaches the problem of differentiation of the terms "terminology" and "terminology system" from different positions. He considers scientific theory or concept to be one of the bases for distinguishing between terminology and terminology system. According to V. M. Leichik, terminology is a set of terms not united by any theory or concept, and accordingly, does not reflect all the concepts of a given science or branch of technology; and a terminology system, on the contrary, is a set of terms formed on the basis of one theory or concept and reflecting the connections of all the concepts of a certain field of knowledge.

As the next distinctive feature of the terminology system, a number of linguists, such as V. M. Leichik and R. Yu. Kobrin, consider its orderliness. According to scientists, terminology appears spontaneously, while the terminology system is created artificially and is formed as a result of ordering terminology into an organized system of terms with relationships between them

recorded in industry dictionaries and classification models. However, according to the opinion of well-known researchers of terms A. V. Superanskaya, N. V. Podolskaya and N. V. Vasilyeva, modern terminology is also created artificially. "The terminology of modern science is an artificially formed lexical layer, each unit of which has certain limitations for its use and optimal conditions for its existence and development.

M. Leychik in his book "Terminology: subject, methods, structure" emphasizes that terminology and terminology system are different sets of terms and that terms in terminology receive their terminological semantics, and in the terminology system they also have other properties, such as systematicity, precision, unambiguity and stylistic neutrality. K. Ya. Averbukh in his monograph "General Theory of the Term" defines a terminology system as a terminology in which its actual systemic properties are clearly revealed.

Terminology as a system was also presented by one of the first domestic terminologists, the founder of the terminological school in our country, D. S. Lotte: "Scientific terminology should not be a simple collection of words, but a system of words and phrases, interconnected in a certain way". Later, D.S. Lotte wrote that terminology is "not just a list of terms, but a semiological expression of a certain system of concepts, which, in turn, reflects a certain scientific worldview" (emphasis added - N. Sh.).

R. Yu. Kobrin defines the terminology field as a system of "scientific and technical special concepts, which in terms of expression corresponds to terminology (a set of interdependent lexical units)". V. M. Leichik believes that the functioning of the terminology field is one of the controversial issues of terminology, "since the concept of the terminology field coincides with the concept of the terminology system". The fact that some scientists define the terminology field as a plan of the content of terminology, while others - as a plan of the content of the terminology system, once again testifies to the absence of a generally accepted and complete definition of the terminology system, clearly distinguishing it from terminology.

References:

1. Averbukh K. Ya. Linguistic and statistical study of the terminology of chemical engineering: diss. ... candidate of philological sciences. Gorky, 1980. 196 .
2. Averbukh K. Ya. General theory of the term. Moscow: Publishing house of Moscow State University, 2006. 252 p.
3. Vinogradova N. V. Term system of German e- commerce [Electronic resource]: author's abstract. diss.... candidate of philological sciences

4. Kobrin R. Yu. Linguistic description of terminology as a basis for conceptual modeling in information systems: author's abstract. diss. ... Doctor of Philological Sciences. Leningrad, 1989. 42 p.
5. Leichik V. M. Optimal length and optimal structure of a term // Voprosy yazykoznaniiya. 1981.

